

Supplementary Material 2. Semi-Structured Interview Guide

The following guide outlines the semi-structured interview questions administered to participants immediately after the SECPT. These questions were designed to capture the range of psychological and physiological responses that may occur during the task, including emotional regulation, physical sensations, attentional focus, and the potential influence of social evaluation.

Sample Interview Questions

1. How did you feel just before you immersed your hand in the cold water?
2. How did your perception of the discomfort change as time passed during the test?
3. How did you feel emotionally during the task? (e.g., anxious, frustrated, determined)
4. What do you think influenced your tolerance to keep your hand in the water the most?
5. Is there anything else you would like to share about your experience during the test that you feel is important for us to understand?